

1 **Cannabinoid CB₂ receptor drives trastuzumab resistance and predicts durable**
2 **anti-HER2 response**

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51 **COMPETING INTERESTS**

52 The authors declare that they have no competing interests

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62 **ABSTRACT**

63 Acquired or innate lack of response to standard HER2-targeted therapies remains a clinical issue
64 in patients with HER2-positive breast cancer. Here, we investigated the role of the cannabinoid
65 CB₂ receptor (CB₂R) in trastuzumab resistance. In human breast cancer samples, a decreased
66 expression of HER2-CB₂R heterodimers following neoadjuvant treatment, due to CB₂R
67 downregulation, was linked to poor long-term outcomes. Using various preclinical models, we
68 demonstrate that CB₂R drives trastuzumab resistance. Mechanistically, CB₂R loss enabled cancer
69 cells to evade antitumor IFN- γ signaling while promoting a shift from HER2-CB₂R to HER2-
70 EGFR heterodimers, thus reducing dependence on HER2 and increasing reliance on EGFR-
71 mediated pathways. Moreover, EGFR inhibition restored trastuzumab sensitivity. In summary,
72 we reveal an unprecedented role for CB₂R as a key regulator of oncogenic and immune signaling
73 in response to anti-HER2 therapy and its potential as a predictive biomarker of therapeutic
74 efficacy. We also propose dual HER2/EGFR targeting and non-CB₂R-selective cannabinoid
75 therapies as potential strategies to overcome CB₂R-mediated trastuzumab resistance. Together,
76 these findings position the endocannabinoid system as a pivotal and actionable node to elucidate,
77 anticipate and counteract resistance to HER2-targeted therapies.

78 INTRODUCTION

79 Breast cancer (BC) is the leading cause of cancer-related death in women [1]. One of the main
80 subtypes of BC is characterized by the overexpression of HER2. This oncogene is a receptor
81 tyrosine kinase that belongs to the HER family, which consists of four members: HER1 (EGFR),
82 HER2, HER3, and HER4. Activation of these receptors occurs upon homo- or heterodimerization,
83 resulting in the activation of pro-oncogenic signaling pathways that drive tumor progression [2].
84 HER2-positive (HER2+) BC management has experienced a significant improvement over the
85 past two decades owing to the development of HER2-targeted therapies. Trastuzumab, a
86 humanized monoclonal antibody that binds to the extracellular domain IV of HER2, was the first
87 approved HER2-targeted therapy and remains the cornerstone of all HER2+ BC treatments [3].
88 The main mechanisms underlying trastuzumab antitumor action include HER2 internalization,
89 the suppression of HER2-driven pro-oncogenic signaling, and the induction of antibody-
90 dependent cell-mediated cytotoxicity (ADCC) [3]. The latter response involves immune cells,
91 primarily natural killer (NK) cells, which are recruited to kill target HER2-overexpressing cells
92 coated with trastuzumab [4].

93 The standard treatment course for most HER2+ BC patients begins with an initial
94 preoperative (neoadjuvant) therapy (NAT), followed by an adjuvant treatment. NAT aims to
95 evaluate treatment efficacy to determine the subsequent adjuvant treatment plan, as well as to
96 reduce the extent of surgical intervention needed. Most NAT regimes involve dual HER2
97 blockade with trastuzumab and pertuzumab (an anti-HER2 antibody targeting the extracellular
98 domain II of the receptor) in combination with chemotherapy. After NAT, patients who achieve
99 pathological complete response (pCR) or have residual disease receive adjuvant treatments that
100 also include trastuzumab [5-7]. Despite these advances, and although early HER2+ BC patients
101 respond successfully to therapy in most cases, the metastatic stage is usually accompanied by
102 treatment resistance and disease progression. Resistance mechanisms include restrictions for
103 trastuzumab binding to HER2, aberrant activation of HER2 downstream signaling pathways,
104 ADCC escape, and a switch to alternative pro-oncogenic drivers [8, 9]. This scenario underscores

105 the need for a deeper understanding of the molecular mechanisms responsible for treatment
106 resistance, as well as for the identification of predictive biomarkers that would enable early
107 detection of which precise patients will respond to specific therapies, thus allowing for
108 personalized treatment selection.

109 Recent studies have highlighted the potential role of the endocannabinoid system (ECS)
110 in HER2+ BC progression. This cell communication system comprises two cannabinoid-sensing
111 G protein-coupled receptors (CB₁R and CB₂R), their endogenous ligands (known as
112 endocannabinoids), and the enzymes responsible for endocannabinoid synthesis and degradation
113 [10]. In the context of BC, previous evidence supports that the pro-oncogenic activity of HER2 is
114 regulated by CB₂R. Specifically, the formation of HER2-CB₂R heterodimers promotes HER2
115 signaling, while disruption of these protein complexes triggers antitumor responses [11, 12].
116 Hence, given the relevance of HER2-CB₂R heterodimers in HER2+ BC physiopathology, this
117 study aims to explore their potential involvement in the resistance to HER2-targeted therapies,
118 particularly those based on trastuzumab.

119

120 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

121 **Human samples**

122 All studies involving human samples were approved by the respective hospital ethics committees
123 (CEIm # 23/213 and 20/615, Hospital 12 de Octubre and Hospital Puerta de Hierro, respectively),
124 with patients providing informed consent without compensation.

125 Two tissue microarrays (TMAs) were constructed using 1 mm cores from paraffin-
126 embedded tissue blocks, arranged into a positionally encoded recipient paraffin block. The
127 samples consisted of tumor biopsies from HER2+ cancer patients collected before and after
128 neoadjuvant treatment (NAT), which included trastuzumab (\pm additional anti-HER2 therapies
129 and/or chemotherapy). **TMA H12O** comprised 37 samples from patients treated at Hospital 12
130 de Octubre (Madrid, Spain) between 1999 and 2013, including 31 paired samples (pre- and post-
131 NAT from the same patient). **TMA HPH** included 42 paired duplicate samples from patients

132 treated at Hospital Puerta de Hierro (Madrid, Spain) between 2012 and 2022 and deposited at the
133 hospital's biobank (Carlos III Health Institute Biomodels and Biobanks Platform – PT23/00015).
134

135 **Cell lines and cultures**

136 Cell lines were obtained from commercial vendors whenever available. Cell lines not directly
137 purchased from certified suppliers were authenticated by short tandem repeat profiling at the
138 Genomics Core Facility of the Instituto de Investigaciones Biomédicas Alberto Sols (Madrid,
139 Spain). All cell lines were cultured at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂ and tested
140 weekly for *Mycoplasma* contamination with PuReTaq Ready-To-Go PCR Beads (#27-9557-02,
141 GE Healthcare, Madrid, Spain) and the following primers: P1, 5' GGC GAA TGG GTG AGT
142 AAC ACG 3' and P2, CGG ATA ACG CTT GCG ACC TAT G 3. After thawing, cell lines were
143 used for a maximum of 25 passages. Human HER2+ female breast cancer cell lines **BT474 TS**
144 (trastuzumab-sensitive, #HTB-20) and **TR** (trastuzumab-resistant, #CRL-3247) were obtained
145 from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, Manassas, VI, USA) in 2021 and 2022,
146 respectively.

147 The CB₂R knockout (**KO**) cell line was generated by knocking out CB₂R expression in
148 TS cells using CRISPR/Cas9. The following RNA guide targeting CB₂R exon 3 was cloned into
149 the pLv-puro-sgRNA lentiviral plasmid: TCC GGA ATC ATC TAC ACC TA TGG) (Addgene
150 #7140, Watertown, MA, USA). TS cells stably expressing Cas9 (via infection with a pCLIP-
151 hCMV-Cas9-Nuclease-Blast lentiviral plasmid, kindly donated by Dr. Markus Müschen, City of
152 Hope Comprehensive Cancer Center, Duarte, CA, USA) were infected with the CB₂R-targeting
153 guide. Cells incorporating both Cas9 and guide were selected via antibiotic resistance, and CB₂R
154 knockout was confirmed by genomic PCR.

155 The scramble control (**SCR**) cell line was generated using the same protocol but with a
156 scramble guide (CCT AAG GTT AAG TCG CCC TCG CTC GAG CGA GGG CGA CTT AAC
157 CT TAGG). The CB₂R rescue (**RESC**) and **TR CB₂R** cell lines were derived from CB₂R KO and
158 TR cells, respectively, via lentiviral transduction of the pLv-neo-CMV-hCNR2 plasmid. Briefly,
159 lentiviral particles were produced by transfecting HEK293T cells with envelope (pMD2.G,

160 Addgene #12259), packaging (psPAX2, Addgene #12260), and donor plasmids (CB₂R, pLv-neo-
161 hCNR2, Vector Builder, Neu-Isenburg, Germany). Conditioned medium containing recombinant
162 lentiviruses was collected, filtered, and used to infect CB₂R KO and TR cells.

163 Trastuzumab sensitive/resistant cells derived from **PDX118** (a patient-derived xenograft
164 established from a HER2⁺ breast tumor) were kindly provided by Dr. Enrique Arenas (Institut de
165 Recerca Contra la Leucèmia Josep Carreras. Barcelona, Spain) and are described in [13].

166 **CHO-K1** (#CCL-61, RRID:CVCL_0214) and **HEK293T** cells (#CRL-3216,
167 RRID:CVCL_0063) (both female) were from obtained from EACR (Nottingham, UK) and
168 ATCC, respectively. The **HEK HER2** and **HEK CB₂R** cell lines were generated by lentiviral
169 transduction of the pLv-Bsd-CMV-hERBB2 and pLv225-puro-HA-hCNR2 plasmids (Vector
170 Builder), respectively, following the protocol described above. **HEK HER2-CB₂R** cells were
171 generated by simultaneous infection with both plasmids.

172 The NK cell line **NK92-CD16-GFP** (male) was also obtained from ATCC in 2016
173 (#CRL-2408, RRID:CVCL_3755).

174 All BT474-derived and PDX-derived cell lines were cultured in DMEM/F12
175 supplemented with FBS, and penicillin/streptomycin. HEK293T cells were grown in DMEM
176 supplemented with FBS, ultraglutamine and penicillin/streptomycin. Cells used for displacement
177 experiments were grown in DMEM/F12 (CHO-K1) or DMEM (HEK293T) supplemented just
178 with FBS. NK92-CD16-GFP cells were cultured in RPMI supplemented with FBS, human serum,
179 IL-2, glutamine, sodium pyruvate, and β-mercaptoethanol.

180

181 **Cell viability assays**

182 Cells were seeded at semi-confluence and cultured for 24 h. Viability was then assessed using
183 crystal violet staining. Briefly, cultures were incubated with 0.1% crystal violet solution in
184 methanol/water for 20 min. After several washes, the resulting crystals were dissolved in
185 methanol, and absorbance was measured at 570 nm.

186 When cells were treated with trastuzumab, erlotinib, or cannabinoids alone, their viability
187 was measured after 5, 3 and 1 days of drug exposure, respectively. For experiments with

188 combined treatments, cell viability was analyzed 4 days after drug challenge. Cannabinoids used
189 were HU308 (CB₂R-selective agonist, Tocris Bioscience #3088, Bristol, UK), Δ⁹-
190 tetrahydrocannabinol (THC, a CB₁R/CB₂R mixed agonist, THC Pharm GmbH #THC-1099,
191 Frankfurt, Germany) and three *Cannabis sativa* extracts: two of them rich in THC (Cannabis
192 Extracts 1 and 2, CE1 and CE2), and one with a balanced THC:CBD ratio (CE3). CE1 was kindly
193 donated by Aunt Zelda's (California, USA), and C2 and C3 by Curativa Group (Colombia). The
194 composition of the three extracts is shown in Supp. Table S2.

195 In tumor cell + NK cell co-culture experiments, tumor cell lines were seeded at semi-
196 confluence in complete medium and incubated with trastuzumab for 1 h. Subsequently, NK92-
197 CD16-GFP cells were added at a 1:4 ratio (tumor:NK cells) in NK cell medium lacking IL-2, and
198 cell viability was assessed 24 h later.

199

200 **Proximity ligation assays (PLAs)**

201 Receptor heteromers were detected using the Duolink In Situ PLA Detection Kit (Sigma-Aldrich,
202 St. Louis, MA, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. For TMAs and animal-derived
203 xenograft sections, samples were deparaffinized, subjected to heat-induced antigen retrieval in
204 sodium citrate buffer, and permeabilized with 0.05% Triton X-100. For cell cultures, cells were
205 seeded on glass coverslips, challenged with the corresponding treatment when indicated, fixed
206 with paraformaldehyde, and permeabilized with Triton X-100. Samples were then incubated with
207 primary antibodies: rabbit anti-CB₂R (Cayman Chemical, #101550-1, RRID:AB_327841), mouse
208 anti-HER2 (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, #sc-08, RRID:AB_627998), rabbit anti-EGFR, and rabbit
209 anti-IFNGR1 (Cell Signaling Technology, #4267, RRID:AB_2246311, and #34808,
210 RRID:AB_2799061, respectively). Secondary antibodies conjugated to PLUS and MINUS
211 complementary nucleotide probes (anti-rabbit PLUS and anti-mouse MINUS; Sigma-Aldrich
212 #DUO92002 and #DUO92004, respectively) were added, followed by ligase and polymerase in
213 the presence of red fluorescent nucleotides. Nuclei were stained with DAPI. Samples were
214 analyzed via confocal microscopy and processed with ImageJ software. Heteromer expression

215 was quantified as the number of red fluorescent dots (indicating receptor proximity sufficient for
216 probe complementation, circularization, and amplification) per total cells in the field.

217 Kaplan-Meier curves for disease-free survival based on heteromer expression were
218 generated using the Kaplan-Meier Plotter (KM plotter) online tool. The best threshold cutoffs
219 were automatically determined by the software.

220

221 **Immunohistochemistry assays**

222 Paraffin-embedded tissue sections were subjected to a heat-induced antigen retrieval and
223 subsequent incubation with either rabbit anti-HER2 (Herceptest, 1:500, Agilent Dako, Santa
224 Clara, CA, USA), rabbit anti-CB₂R (Cayman Chemical, #101550-1, RRID:AB_327841, 1:2500)
225 or rabbit anti-EGFR (Leica Biosystems, #NCL-EGFR, RRID:AB_442085, or Cell Signaling
226 Technology, #4267, RRID:AB_2246311) antibodies.

227 Immunodetection was performed using the Envision method with diaminobenzidine as
228 the chromogen. CB₂R and EGFR expression were quantified in the TMAs assigning scores to
229 each sample [0 (no staining), 1 (weak staining), 2 (moderate staining), or 3 (high staining)]. HER2
230 staining was scored in accordance with the HercepTest manufacturer's guidelines.

231 Kaplan-Meier plots for disease-free survival based on HER2, CB₂R, or EGFR expression
232 were generated as explained in the PLA methods section.

233

234 **Real-time quantitative PCR (qPCR)**

235 RNA extraction was performed using the NucleoZOL kit (#740404, Macherey-Nagel, Dueren,
236 Germany) following the manufacturer's instructions. Reverse transcription to cDNA was carried
237 out using the Transcriptor First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (#4897030001, Roche Life Science,
238 Barcelona, Spain). qPCR was performed with the following primers and SYBR Green probe
239 (Roche Life Science #4913914001): *CNR2*: sense CAC TGA TCC CCA ATG ACT ACC T,
240 antisense CAT GCC CAT AGG TGT AGA TG; *ERBB2*: sense GGG AAA CCT GGA ACT CAC
241 CT, antisense CCC TGC ACC TCC TGG ATA; *ERBB1*: sense ACA CAG AAT CTA TAC CCA
242 CCA GAG T, antisense ATC AAC TCC CAA ACG GTC AC; *ERBB3*: sense TGA ATG GCC

243 TGA GTG TGA CC, antisense CCC CTG ACA GAA TCT CGG TG; *ERBB4*: sense GAG CAA
244 GAA TTG ACT CGA ATA GG, antisense TTC CTG ACA TGG GGG TGT AG; *IFNGR1*: sense
245 CCT TGT CAT GCA GGG TGT GA, antisense TTG GTG TAG GCA CTG AGG AC; *JAK1*:
246 sense GGC TTC TGA GAC ACA CGC TT, antisense CAG CTG TCC AGT GTT CTC CA;
247 *JAK2*: sense GCC GGG TTT CAG AAG CAG G, antisense TTC AGA ACA TTT GCC GTC
248 GC; *STAT1*: sense GCT CGT TTG TGG TGG AAA GAC, antisense TCT CTC ATT CAC ATC
249 TCT CAA CTT; *ACTB*: sense CCA ACC GCG AGA AGAT GA, antisense CCA GAG GCG
250 TAC AGG GAT AG; *TBP*: sense CCC ATG ACT CCC ATG ACC, antisense TTT ACA ACC
251 AAG ATT CAC TGT GG. Gene expression was calculated using the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method and
252 normalized to reference genes TBP (TATA-binding protein) and ACTB (β -Actin).

253

254 **RNA sequencing (RNAseq)**

255 RNA from cell cultures was isolated as described above. Concentration and RNA integrity (>7)
256 were determined, and 1 μ g per sample was utilized for RNA-seq. Sequencing and results analysis
257 (with Genome One software) were performed by Dreamgenics S.L. (Oviedo, Spain). The
258 generated datasets are available through the Gene Expression Omnibus repository under the
259 accession number GSE300749. Gene expression level was represented as a colored cell, with a
260 color key interpretation indicated where appropriate. The identification of the biological processes
261 modulated by the differentially expressed genes was performed by using the pathfindR tool and
262 the repositories of Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) and Gene Ontology
263 (GO), and GSEA (Gene Set Enrichment Analysis).

264

265 **Proteomic analyses**

266 Cultured cells were lysed in GST lysis buffer [10% glycerol, 100 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 50
267 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 1% tergitol (Sigma-Aldrich, #NP40S)] supplemented with protease and
268 phosphatase inhibitors. Samples were centrifuged, and protein concentration in supernatants was
269 determined using the Bradford method. Total protein was split into two fractions: one for
270 validating target protein expression (input) and another (IP) to proceed with a protein co-

271 immunoprecipitation (co-IP), that started with an incubation with G-Sepharose beads (or anti-HA
272 antibody-bound beads for HEK293T HA-CB₂R cells). After bead incubation, beads were
273 removed, and samples were incubated with primary antibodies. G-Sepharose beads were then
274 reintroduced, and target proteins were co-immunoprecipitated via centrifugation. Proteins were
275 then eluted by boiling in Laemmli loading buffer. Analysis of the co-IP procedure was performed
276 by Western blot (see below).

277 Following co-IP, proteins were separated by SDS-PAGE and stained with Coomassie
278 Brilliant Blue G-250 to confirm proper protein separation. Gel lanes were excised, destained,
279 dehydrated, and subjected to reduction/alkylation. After rehydration, proteins were digested with
280 trypsin, and resulting peptides were extracted, purified, and analyzed by mass spectrometry.

281 LC-MS/MS parameters followed the protocol by Montero-Calle *et al.* [14]. Peptides were
282 separated using a nano Easy-nLC 1000 system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain) with an
283 Acclaim PepMap 100 precolumn (Thermo Fisher Scientific #164946) and an RSLC PepMap C18
284 column (Thermo Fisher Scientific #11362013). Mobile phase flow rate was 300 nL/min, with
285 0.1% formic acid (FA) in water (buffer A) and 0.1% FA in 100% acetonitrile (buffer B) for
286 peptide elution over a 102-min gradient. MS/MS analysis was performed on a Q Exactive using
287 data-dependent acquisition, selecting the top 15 most intense precursor ions for fragmentation
288 after each scan.

289 Mass spectrometry data were analyzed with Proteome Discoverer (v1.4.1.14, Thermo
290 Fisher Scientific). Raw spectra files were searched against the *Swiss-*
291 *Prot_2016_10.fasta* database (Homo sapiens, 20121 protein sequences) using Mascot (v2.6,
292 Matrix Science). Precursor and fragment mass tolerances were set to 10 ppm and 0.02 Da,
293 respectively. Parameters included two missed cleavages, fixed carbamidomethylation of
294 cysteines, and variable methionine oxidation/N-terminal acetylation. Peptides were filtered using
295 Percolator (q-value threshold: 0.01). Venn diagrams were generated using the jvenn web tool.
296 Reactome Pathway Database was used to identify signaling pathways associated with potential
297 interactors.

298

299 **Western blot**

300 Cells were scraped into DDM buffer (or RIPA buffer for JAK/STAT protein analysis)
301 supplemented with protease and phosphatase inhibitors. Protein extracts were separated by SDS-
302 PAGE and transferred to PVDF membranes using a Trans-Blot® SD Semi-Dry Transfer Cell
303 (Bio-Rad, Madrid, Spain). Membranes were then incubated with the appropriate primary
304 antibodies: mouse anti-EGFR (4267, RRID:AB_2246311), rabbit anti-JAK1 (3344,
305 RRID:AB_2265054), rabbit anti-JAK2 (3230, RRID:AB_2128522), rabbit anti-p-STAT1 (9167,
306 RRID:AB_561284), rabbit anti-STAT1 (9172, RRID:AB_2198300), rabbit anti-IRF1 (8478,
307 RRID:AB_10949108), all from Cell Signaling Technology; rabbit anti-CB₂R (SAB1306696),
308 mouse anti-Vinculine (V9264, RRID:AB_10603627), and mouse anti-β Actin (A5441,
309 RRID:AB_476744), all from Sigma-Aldrich. After several washes, membranes were incubated
310 with the corresponding HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies, and the signal was developed
311 using a self-prepared ECL reagent. The bioluminescence was captured with the ImageQuant LAS
312 500 system (GE HealthCare) and the densitometric analysis was performed using Image Lab™
313 software (Bio-Rad).

314

315 **Biotinylation assays**

316 HER2 expression specifically at the plasma membrane was assessed by protein biotinylation
317 assays. Following an initial 15 min incubation on ice, cells were exposed to sulfobiotin for 30 min
318 in the dark. Cells were then washed with L-lysine and lysed in DDM buffer supplemented with
319 protease and phosphatase inhibitors, and protein concentration was determined by Bradford assay.

320 A portion of each sample was reserved to assess the expression of proteins of interest
321 (input), while the remainder was incubated with streptavidin beads to capture biotinylated
322 proteins. Samples were centrifuged, washed with DDM buffer lacking inhibitors, and prepared in
323 Laemmli loading buffer. After denaturation they were subjected to SDS-PAGE and transferred to
324 PVDF membranes, that were processed as described in the Western blot section. Results were
325 normalized using sodium-potassium ATPase and a loading control as references.

326

327 **Flow cytometry assays**

328 Trastuzumab-HER2 binding was analyzed by flow cytometry using fluorescein isothiocyanate-
329 conjugated trastuzumab (trastuzumab-FITC; #10-2002-F, Abeomics, San Diego, CA, USA).
330 Briefly, cells were detached from culture plates using TripLE™ Express (#12-605-010, Gibco,
331 Eindhoven, The Netherlands) and transferred to 96-well V-bottom plates in staining buffer [PBS
332 containing FBS, BSA, and sodium azide). Plates were centrifuged and pellets were incubated with
333 trastuzumab-FITC for 30 min in the dark. Samples were then transferred to round-bottom
334 polystyrene tubes and stained with 7-aminoactinomycin D (7-AAD) as a viability marker 15 min
335 prior to analysis. Flow cytometry was performed on a FACSCalibur system (Becton Dickinson,
336 Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA), with data processed using FlowJo™ software (BD Biosciences, San
337 Jose, CA, USA).

338

339 **Trastuzumab affinity displacement assays with NanoBiT**

340 HiBiT-EGFR was a gift from Promega (Fitchburg, WI, USA). More details on the generation
341 protocol can be found in [15]. DNA encoding CB₂R (Uni Prot ID:P34972) flanked with PvuI and
342 XbaI restriction sites (start codon mutated to leucine, internal XbaI site silently mutated) was
343 purchased from Twist BioScience (San Francisco, CA, USA). DNA encoding HER2 (Uni Prot
344 ID:P04626) was from Addgene (plasmid #16257).

345 DNA was digested with *PvuI* and *XbaI* (New England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA, USA) and
346 ligated into an expression vector containing an IL-6 signal peptide and N-terminal LrgBiT tag (as
347 described in [16]) to create LrgBiT-CB₂R. For generation of HiBiT-HER2, the HER2 sequence
348 (without its native signal peptide) was amplified using the following primers: forward 5'-GGC
349 GGC TCG AGC GGT GCG ATC ACC CAA GTG TGC ACC GGC-3'; reverse 5'-TGC ATG
350 CCT GCA GGT CGA CTT CAC ACT GGC ACG TCC AG-3'. The N-terminal HiBiT plasmid
351 backbone (generated as described in [16]) was digested with *PvuI* and *XbaI*, and the HER2 PCR
352 product was cloned in using Gibson assembly. To generate LrgBiT-HER2, the HER2 sequence
353 was amplified essentially as described above but with the forward primer 5'-GGC TCG AGC
354 GGT GGC GCG ATC ACC CAA GTG TGC ACC GGC-3' and cloned in frame with the IL-6

355 signal peptide into the N-terminal LrgBiT plasmid backbone using Gibson assembly. Plasmids
356 were verified by Oxford Nanopore Sequencing (Plasmidsaurus, London, UK).

357 HEK293T or CHO-K1 cells were plated into 6-well plates at a density of 5×10^5
358 (HEK293T) or 2.5×10^5 (CHO-K1) cells/well. The next day cells were transfected at a 1:1 ratio of
359 HiBiT:LrgBiT-tagged receptor plasmids using FuGENE HD at a 3:1 DNA:reagent ratio following
360 manufacturer's instructions (Promega). The next day, cells were plated at 4×10^4 cells/well into
361 poly-D-lysine-coated (10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; Sigma-Aldrich) white, clear, flat bottomed 96-well plates
362 (Grenier Bio-one (655098); Stonehouse, UK). On the fourth day, cells were treated with 10 nM
363 trastuzumab-FITC (Stratech, Ely, UK) prepared in HEPES buffered saline solution (HBSS; 2 mM
364 sodium pyruvate, 145 mM NaCl, 10 mM D-glucose, 5 mM KCl, 1 mM $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 10 mM
365 HEPES, 1.3 mM CaCl_2 , 1.5 mM NaHCO_3 in double-distilled water, pH 7.45) supplemented with
366 0.1% BSA in the presence or absence of trastuzumab (Stratech) for 1 h at 37°C . Furimazine
367 (Promega) was then added (1:400 final dilution) and luminescence and fluorescence emissions
368 simultaneously measured on the PheraStar FSX (BMG Labtech, Ortenberg, Germany) using an
369 optic module fitted with 475 nm (± 30 nm; luminescence detection) and 535 nm (± 30 nm;
370 fluorescence detection) band pass filters. BRET ratios were calculated by dividing fluorescence
371 by luminescence emissions.

372 Binding affinities (K_i) of trastuzumab were calculated using the Cheng-Prusoff equation:

373
$$K_i = \frac{IC_{50}}{1 + \frac{[L]}{K_D}}$$

374 where [L] was the concentration of trastuzumab-FITC used (nM), IC_{50} the molar concentration of
375 trastuzumab that inhibited 50% of the specific binding of trastuzumab-FITC, and K_D (nM) the
376 affinity of trastuzumab-FITC determined in saturation binding experiments (HiBiT-HER2 –
377 LrgBiT-HER2 $K_D = 5.73$ nM; HiBiT-HER2 – LrgBiT-CB₂R $K_D = 13.17$ nM; HiBiT-EGFR –
378 LrgBiT-HER2 $K_D = 5.29$ nM; data not shown). Data were normalized for each experimental
379 replicate to total binding of 10 nM trastuzumab-FITC (100%) and vehicle (0%).

380

381 **Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA)**

382 IFN- γ levels in the cancer cell + NK cell co-cultures were assessed by using the Human IFN- γ
383 Standard TMB ELISA Development Kit (PeproTech, Cranbury, NJ, USA) following
384 manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, co-cultures were established as described in the Cell viability
385 assays section, and culture media collected 24 h later. Conditioned media was incubated for 2 h
386 in 96-well, flat-bottom ELISA microplates previously coated with anti-human IFN- γ antibody.
387 Detection was carried out by subsequent incubation with a detection antibody and streptavidin-
388 HRP conjugate. Color development was monitor with an ELISA plate reader.

389

390 **Animals**

391 All animal procedures were conducted with the approval of the Complutense University Animal
392 Experimentation Committee and the Madrid Regional Government, in compliance with European
393 regulations. The maximal tumor burden permitted was $1 \times 10^3 \text{ mm}^3$ and it was never exceeded.
394 Animals were housed in the UCM School of Biology animal facility under a 12-h light-dark cycle,
395 with ad libitum access to food and water. Sample size was calculated using the GRANMO Sample
396 Size Calculator (version 8), assuming a two-sided test with an alpha risk of 0.05 and a beta risk
397 of 0.2, a common standard deviation of 1.4, and an estimated 20% dropout rate.

398 Xenografts were generated by subcutaneous injection of 2×10^6 TR or TR CB₂R cells
399 (resuspended in Matrigel) into the right flank of 6-week-old female athymic nude-Foxn1nu mice
400 (RRID:IMSR_ENV:HSP-069, Envigo, Barcelona, Spain). Due to estrogen receptor (ER)
401 expression in BT474 cells, drinking water was supplemented with 17 β -estradiol (Sigma-Aldrich)
402 starting one week before cancer cell inoculation and continuing until sacrifice. Tumors were
403 monitored regularly using a digital caliper, and their volume was calculated as $(4\pi/3) \times (\text{width}/2)^2$
404 $\times (\text{length}/2)$. Once tumors reached a volume of 100–200 mm³, animals were randomly assigned
405 to experimental groups by sequential allocation to the different treatment arms without additional
406 selection criteria, and treatment commenced. Blinding was not implemented during treatment
407 administration, as knowledge of group allocation was required to ensure correct dosing and
408 treatment delivery.

409 For **xenografts derived from TR cells**, six treatment groups were established with the
410 following schedules: Trastuzumab (20 mg/kg in saline, intraperitoneally (IP), twice weekly);
411 Erlotinib (50 mg/kg in PEG/saline 1:1, IP, five times weekly); Erlotinib followed by trastuzumab
412 (One week of erlotinib followed by three weeks of trastuzumab); Trastuzumab followed by
413 erlotinib (One week of trastuzumab followed by three weeks of erlotinib); Trastuzumab +
414 erlotinib (Four weeks of combined treatment); Vehicle (PEG/saline, IP, five times weekly).

415 For **xenografts derived from TR CB₂R cells**, two groups were established: Trastuzumab
416 and Vehicle, following the same dosing schedules as above.

417 After four weeks of treatment (or earlier if tumor volumes exceeded 1×10^3 mm³), mice were
418 euthanized. Tumors were excised and divided into two portions when possible—one for protein
419 extraction and the other for RNA isolation—and snap-frozen until subsequent processing.

420

421 **Statistical analyses**

422 Sample size was determined based on prior experience using similar HER2+ breast cancer
423 models. No samples or animals were excluded from the analyses.

424 Pearson's chi-squared test was used for statistical analysis of the human samples included
425 in the TMAs. Kaplan-Meier survival curves were statistically compared by the log-rank test. For
426 the rest of data, normality was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. For normally distributed
427 datasets, independent two-group comparisons were performed using Student's *t*-test, while for
428 multi-group analyses one-way or two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test were used.
429 Non-normally distributed data were analyzed via the Mann-Whitney *U* test for two independent
430 groups or the Kruskal-Wallis test with Dunn's post hoc correction for multi-group comparisons.
431 All statistical tests were two-tailed, with significance thresholds set at $p < 0.05$. Unless otherwise
432 stated, data are expressed as mean \pm SEM. Statistical analysis was performed with GraphPad
433 Prism version 8.0.1. or 10.4.2.

434

435 **RESULTS**

436 **A reduction in HER2-CB₂R expression after NAT is linked to treatment resistance**

437 To investigate the potential involvement of the HER2-CB₂R heterodimer in trastuzumab
438 resistance, we analyzed its expression by proximity ligation assays (PLAs) in two tissue
439 microarrays (TMAs) containing two independent cohorts of human HER2+ tumor samples
440 obtained after NAT, which included trastuzumab in all cases. Patients with lower disease-free
441 survival, indicating a poorer response to therapy and/or an increased resistance, had lower HER2-
442 CB₂R levels compared to responsive patients, which had higher long-term survival (Figs. 1A-B).
443 Our previous work had found that high HER2-CB₂R expression at initial biopsy (before NAT) is
444 associated with poor patient prognosis and, therefore, more aggressive phenotypes [11]. Together,
445 these findings led us to hypothesize that treatment resistance might be linked to a decrease in
446 HER2-CB₂R expression after NAT. Analysis of 73 matched pre- and post-NAT samples
447 supported this idea: patients who responded to therapy (i.e., with no long-term disease
448 progression) showed varied changes in HER2-CB₂R expression (upregulation, downregulation,
449 or no change), while those with treatment failure (i.e., with disease progression) consistently
450 showed a decline in HER2-CB₂R expression after NAT (Fig. 1C). This drop was further
451 associated with lower disease-free survival (Fig. 1D).

452 The separate analysis of HER2 and CB₂R expression in these samples (Supp. Fig. S1)
453 indicated that the decrease in HER2-CB₂R after NAT was primarily due to reduced CB₂R levels.
454 Thus, we did not observe a consistent change in HER2 levels in patients with or without disease
455 progression (Fig. 1E). Consequently, changes in HER2 expression after NAT were not associated
456 with differences in disease-free survival (Fig. 1F). Regarding CB₂R expression, changes after
457 NAT mirrored those of the heteromer in one of the TMAs (H12O): no clear pattern in responders
458 (i.e., those without long-term disease progression) and a decrease in non-responders (i.e., those
459 with disease progression) (Fig. 1G). However, in the other sample collection (HPH), this
460 association was not observed (Fig. 1G). Nonetheless, a reduction in CB₂R levels after NAT was
461 associated with lower disease-free survival in both patient cohorts (Fig. 1H). These findings
462 collectively suggest that CB₂R and HER2-CB₂R may serve as novel predictors of long-term

463 response to treatment, and that the decrease in HER2-CB₂R dimers following NAT may
464 contribute to the development of treatment resistance. Nonetheless, the prognostic value of the
465 proposed biomarkers should be interpreted with caution owing to the relatively small sample size
466 and the limited number of events in each cohort, which constrained the complexity of
467 multivariable survival analyses. These limitations warrant confirmation in larger, independent
468 cohorts.

469 **CB₂R loss leads to trastuzumab resistance**

470 We examined the hypothesis that a reduced HER2-CB₂R heterodimer formation post-NAT drives
471 treatment resistance using a pair of BT474-derived breast cancer cell lines, one sensitive (TS) and
472 another resistant (TR) to trastuzumab (Fig. 2A). Consistent with our previous observations (Fig.
473 1), resistant cells exhibited lower levels of HER2-CB₂R (Fig. 2B) and CB₂R (Figs. 2C and D).
474 We also found a cause-effect link between reduced HER2-CB₂R expression due to decreased
475 CB₂R and trastuzumab resistance: re-expression of CB₂R in resistant cells restored HER2-CB₂R
476 levels and trastuzumab sensitivity (Figs. 2A-D), and genetic silencing of CB₂R in sensitive cells
477 decreased HER2-CB₂R levels and induced trastuzumab resistance, effects that were both reversed
478 upon CB₂R re-expression (Figs. 2D-G). Trastuzumab resistance linked to reduced HER2-CB₂R
479 and CB₂R expression was further validated in a HER2⁺ breast cancer patient-derived xenograft
480 (PDX) model, PDX118, consisting of a TS and TR pair of cell lines (Supp. Fig. S2A). Thus, TR
481 cells showed decreased HER2-CB₂R (Fig. Supp. S2B) and CB₂R expression (Fig. Supp. S2C and
482 D) when compared to their corresponding TS counterparts.

483 To elucidate trastuzumab resistance mechanisms associated with CB₂R loss, we first
484 examined whether a reduced HER2 availability -potentially caused by decreased HER2-CB₂R
485 complex formation- may underlie therapeutic resistance. In line with this idea, trastuzumab-
486 resistant cells (TR and CB₂R KO) exhibited significantly reduced trastuzumab-FITC binding than
487 their sensitive counterparts (TS and SCR, respectively) (Fig. 3A). This was not due to a decrease
488 in HER2 expression, as mRNA (Figs. 2C and E), total protein (Fig. 3B), and plasma membrane-
489 located protein (Fig. 3C) were all comparable across cell lines. The reduced trastuzumab binding

490 to resistant cells was not due to a decreased affinity either. Thus, ligand displacement experiments
491 in HEK293T and CHO-K1 cells expressing NanoBiT-tagged HER2 and CB₂R revealed nearly
492 identical pK_i values for trastuzumab in cells transfected with HER2-HER2 or HER2-CB₂R
493 complementary vectors (Fig. 3D), demonstrating comparable binding affinity regardless of CB₂R
494 presence. Hence, these findings point to the existence of alterations in trastuzumab-to-HER2
495 binding associated with trastuzumab resistance, and to the relevance of CB₂R expression as a key
496 mediator in this process.

497 **Trastuzumab resistance linked to reduced CB₂R is due to evasion of antitumor IFN- γ** 498 **signaling**

499 To investigate whether trastuzumab resistance involves the activation of compensatory signaling
500 pathways in our models, we first conducted a proteomic study in HEK293T cells expressing HA-
501 CB₂R and HER2, either individually or together (Fig. 4A). We identified a set of 32 proteins
502 potentially interacting with CB₂R, a set of 33 proteins potentially interacting with HER2, and a
503 set of 123 potentially interacting proteins when both receptors were co-expressed (Fig. 4B and
504 Supp. Table S1). This suggests the existence of a unique HER2-CB₂R interactome and, therefore,
505 of a potential heteromer-driven signaling distinct from monomeric signaling. Using Reactome
506 software, we found that these 123 proteins modulate key cancer-related pathways, including
507 interferon- γ (IFN- γ), fibroblast growth factor receptor (FGFR), and small G protein signaling
508 (Fig. 4C).

509 To explore the relevance of a HER2-CB₂R-driven signaling in trastuzumab resistance,
510 we performed RNA sequencing (RNAseq) on our cancer cell models. This analysis revealed
511 differential expression of 8,983 genes between trastuzumab-sensitive and trastuzumab-resistant
512 cells (Fig. 4D). Notably, 17 genetic signatures related to oncogenesis differed significantly
513 between the two groups (Fig. 4E). The IFN- γ response signature was one of them and appeared
514 underrepresented in resistant cell lines. Gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) confirmed this
515 finding, showing reduced expression of this signature in trastuzumab-resistant cells (Fig. 4F).
516 These observations suggest that trastuzumab resistance may involve impaired responsiveness to

517 IFN- γ antitumor signaling. However, a comprehensive pathway analysis revealed no consistent
518 alterations in the key elements of this route that were CB₂R-dependent. For example, no
519 significant differences were observed between sensitive and resistant cell lines in the mRNA
520 expression of IFN- γ receptors (Fig. 5A and Supp. Fig. S2E). Regarding the downstream
521 JAK/STAT proteins, qPCR (Fig. 5B and Supp. Fig. S2F) and Western blot (Fig. 5C and Supp.
522 Fig. S2G) experiments showed similar JAK1 expression in all cell lines. JAK2 mRNA and protein
523 levels appeared reduced in both BT474-derived trastuzumab-resistant cell lines (TR and CB₂R
524 KO) compared to their sensitive counterparts (TS and SCR, respectively) (Figs. 5B-C), as well as
525 in the PDX-derived TR model (Supp. Figs. S2F and 2G), but CB₂R re-expression did not bring
526 its expression back to basal levels (Figs. 5B and C). Regarding STATs, we focused on STAT1, a
527 crucial mediator of IFN- γ signaling, and the data did not show any significant difference in its
528 mRNA (Fig. 5B and Supp. Fig. S2F) or protein levels (Fig. 5C and Supp. Fig. S2G) between cell
529 lines.

530 Although we were not able to identify any basal differences in the expression of key IFN-
531 γ signaling components between cell lines that could account for CB₂R-dependent trastuzumab
532 resistance, we found a distinct IFN- γ response profile between cell groups. Thus, upon IFN- γ
533 stimulation, sensitive cells were able to activate this cascade, increasing the active form of STAT1
534 (pSTAT1) and the downstream target IRF1. In contrast, resistant cells showed minimal changes
535 in these proteins (Fig. 5D). Notably, the sensitivity to IFN- γ was dependent on CB₂R, as its re-
536 expression in resistant cells restored their capability to activate the pathway, thus enhancing
537 STAT1 and IRF1 expression (Fig. 5D).

538 NK cells are a primary source of IFN- γ in tumors and key effectors in ADCC, a pivotal
539 mechanism of trastuzumab's antitumor action. Specifically, NK cells recognize trastuzumab-
540 coated tumor cells through the interaction of trastuzumab with CD16 (Fc γ RIIIa) receptors on
541 their surface, thus triggering the release of cytotoxic molecules from lytic granules, as well as
542 proinflammatory cytokines, including IFN- γ , ultimately inducing target cell death [17]. Co-
543 cultures of our cancer cells with a CD16+ NK cell line showed signs of impaired ADCC in

544 resistant cells. In these experiments, and to isolate ADCC effects, we restricted trastuzumab
545 exposure to 1 h and assessed viability at 24 h—conditions under which trastuzumab monotherapy
546 alone failed to induce cytotoxicity in cancer cell monocultures, regardless of sensitivity status
547 (Fig. 5E). In this setting, sensitive cells exhibited marked trastuzumab-induced cytotoxicity,
548 suggesting functional ADCC activation. In contrast, resistant cells maintained high viability in
549 the co-cultures, indicative of a defective ADCC response (Fig. 5E). These effects were
550 accompanied by an impaired release of IFN- γ to the extracellular medium in co-cultures with
551 resistant cells (Fig. 5F). The pivotal role of CB₂R in these differential responses was evidenced
552 by the impaired ADCC-associated features that were observed in cells lacking CB₂R and were
553 restored upon CB₂R overexpression (Figs. 5E-F).

554 Collectively, these findings indicate that trastuzumab resistance associated with reduced
555 CB₂R is driven, at least partially, by impaired NK-cell mediated cytotoxicity and evasion of
556 antitumor IFN- γ signaling.

557 **Trastuzumab resistance due to reduced CB₂R expression relies on the formation of** 558 **alternative HER2 receptor heterodimers**

559 A well-established mechanism of trastuzumab resistance involves the formation of alternative
560 receptor heterodimers. By engaging in dimerization with other members of the HER family or
561 with other RTKs, cancer cells reduce their reliance on the original HER2-containing dimers for
562 growth and survival signaling, thereby evading trastuzumab's inhibitory effects [9]. We observed
563 that resistance to trastuzumab linked to evasion of antitumor IFN- γ signaling was associated with
564 a decrease in HER2-IFNGR1 heterodimers (Fig. 6A and Supp. Fig. S2H), an effect that was
565 dependent on CB₂R expression (Fig. 6A). Furthermore, IFN- γ stimulation increased the formation
566 of HER2-IFNGR1 heterodimers in sensitive but not in resistant cells (Fig. 6A). These
567 observations support that CB₂R loss-mediated trastuzumab resistance stems from impaired
568 responsiveness to IFN- γ 's antitumor signaling.

569 Our results also revealed a shift in the expression profile of HER family receptors
570 between TS and TR cells. This altered pattern in TR cells was characterized by changes in

571 individual HER members, including increased EGFR expression in BT474-based models (Figs.
572 6B and C) and elevated HER3 levels in the PDX118-derived model (Supp. Figs. S2I and J). This
573 observation was accompanied by an increased HER2-EGFR or HER2-HER3 heterodimer
574 formation (Fig. 6D and Supp. Fig. S2K). As predicted, the dimer switch to HER2-EGFR made
575 trastuzumab-resistant cells more dependent on EGFR pro-survival signaling. Thus, resistant cells
576 showed heightened sensitivity to the antiproliferative effect of erlotinib (a selective EGFR
577 inhibitor) (Fig. 6E) and lapatinib (a dual HER2/EGFR inhibitor) (Supp. Fig. S3A), and this
578 signaling shift was CB₂R dependent, as the increase in EGFR levels (Figs. 6B and C), HER2-
579 EGFR dimerization (Fig. 6D) and erlotinib sensitivity (Fig. 6E) occurred in response to CB₂R
580 loss and were prevented upon CB₂R re-expression. In line with these observations, tucatinib, a
581 HER2-selective inhibitor that does not target EGFR, produced comparable effects in trastuzumab-
582 sensitive and -resistant cells (Supp. Fig. S3B). These results further support the notion that
583 trastuzumab resistance is associated with a shift toward EGFR dependency and suggest that dual
584 HER2/EGFR inhibition may represent an effective therapeutic strategy in CB₂R-low,
585 trastuzumab-resistant contexts.

586 We also investigated whether trastuzumab resistance could result from reduced affinity
587 of trastuzumab for HER2 when dimerized with EGFR, as opposed to HER2-HER2 homodimers.
588 Displacement assays in HEK293T and CHO-K1 cells overexpressing either HER2-HER2 or
589 HER2-EGFR complexes demonstrated that this was not the case, as trastuzumab exhibited
590 virtually identical affinity for both dimeric forms (Fig. 6F).

591 In line with our observations pointing to a signaling switch towards HER2-EGFR
592 signaling in our trastuzumab resistance contexts, elevated HER2-EGFR heterodimer expression
593 in human samples after NAT was significantly associated with reduced overall patient survival
594 (Figs. 7A and B), indicating increased treatment resistance. As opposed to HER2-CB₂R, the
595 changes in HER2-EGFR expression (Supp. Fig. S1) before and after NAT did not follow any
596 pattern with predictive value (Figs. 7C and D), and EGFR expression alone after NAT did not
597 show predictive significance either (Figs. 7E and F). Collectively, these findings further support

598 the relevance of a receptor dimer shift as a pivotal mechanism underlying the acquisition of
599 trastuzumab resistance, and suggest that monitoring HER2-EGFR dimer expression after NAT
600 could provide valuable prognostic insights into therapeutic resistance and patient outcomes.

601 **Trastuzumab resistance linked to reduced CB₂R is overcome by targeting EGFR and HER2**
602 **signaling and by non-CB₂R-selective cannabinoid treatment**

603 The identification of a signaling switch responsible for trastuzumab resistance led us to
604 hypothesize that targeting the newly emerged pro-oncogenic driver (EGFR) could overcome this
605 resistance. This notion was subsequently validated both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. First, the combination
606 of trastuzumab and erlotinib significantly reduced the viability of trastuzumab-resistant cells in
607 culture, with this reduction exceeding that produced by erlotinib alone (Fig. 8A). These findings
608 suggest a synergistic effect that may result from trastuzumab resensitization. This mechanism was
609 further substantiated by the two following observations: first, erlotinib treatment restored the
610 functionality of the JAK/STAT signaling pathway in trastuzumab-resistant cells, as evidenced by
611 IFN- γ recovering its ability to modulate pSTAT1 and IRF1 levels (Fig. 8B). Second, erlotinib
612 administration in resistant cells reestablished both CB₂R expression (Fig. 8C) and HER2-CB₂R
613 heterodimer formation (Fig. 8D).

614 *In vivo* studies provided further support to the critical role of CB₂R in trastuzumab
615 resistance and validated that targeting EGFR signaling represents a promising therapeutic strategy
616 to overcome this resistance. Thus, CB₂R overexpression in trastuzumab-resistant cells
617 successfully restored sensitivity to trastuzumab antitumor action. Strikingly, in many animals, we
618 observed not only an impaired tumor growth but a complete tumor regression (Fig. 8E).
619 Furthermore, simultaneous targeting of EGFR (with erlotinib) and HER2 (with trastuzumab)
620 effectively reversed treatment resistance, resulting in numerous complete tumor regressions (Fig.
621 8F). Similar efficacy was achieved when erlotinib treatment preceded trastuzumab administration,
622 but not when the sequence was reversed (i.e., trastuzumab followed by erlotinib) (Fig. 8F), further
623 supporting the idea that EGFR inhibition restores trastuzumab sensitivity.

624 Cannabinoids are well known to induce antitumor responses in preclinical cancer models
625 [18, 19]. In HER2+ breast cancer, these effects are largely mediated by activation of CB₂R [20].
626 We therefore hypothesized that trastuzumab-resistant cells with reduced/absent CB₂R expression
627 would be less/no responsive to therapies based on CB₂R-selective activation. Accordingly, the
628 CB₂R-selective agonist HU308 reduced cell viability in trastuzumab-sensitive models (TS, SCR
629 and RESC), whereas this effect was attenuated/abolished in resistant cells with low/absent CB₂R
630 expression (TR and CB₂R KO) (Fig. 8G). These findings suggest that trastuzumab-resistant
631 tumors with low CB₂R levels are unlikely to respond to antitumor strategies based solely on CB₂R
632 activation. However, this does not exclude cannabinoids as potential therapeutic agents, as certain
633 cannabinoid compounds and *Cannabis sativa* preparations exert antitumor effects through
634 additional molecular targets. To explore this possibility, resistant cells were treated with Δ⁹-
635 tetrahydrocannabinol (THC), a CB₁R/CB₂R-mixed agonist, and three distinct *Cannabis*
636 *sativa* extracts, including two THC-rich preparations and one with a 1:1 THC:cannabidiol (CBD)
637 ratio. In addition to the indicated cannabinoids, these extracts contained other minor cannabinoids
638 and terpenes (Supp. Table S2). In contrast to HU308, these treatments -although to a lesser extent-
639 also reduced viability in trastuzumab-resistant cells (Fig. 8G). Together, these results suggest that
640 cannabinoids may retain antitumor activity in trastuzumab-resistant HER2+ breast cancer through
641 CB₂R-independent mechanisms.

642 Collectively, these data suggest that HER2+ BC patients who exhibit decreased HER2-
643 CB₂R heterodimers and CB₂R expression after NAT, accompanied by increased EGFR levels and
644 HER2-EGFR dimerization, have a higher likelihood of developing resistance to anti-HER2
645 treatment in the long term. These patients could potentially benefit from therapeutic strategies
646 that simultaneously target both HER2 and EGFR signaling pathways and by cannabinoids that do
647 not selectively target CB₂R.

648

649 **DISCUSSION**

650 HER2+ BC is one of the tumor types that has significantly benefited from the development of
651 targeted therapies. However, important clinical challenges remain unaddressed. While early-stage
652 HER2+ disease responds reasonably well to anti-HER2 treatments, metastatic disease continues
653 to be associated with disease progression in most cases. This therapeutic limitation is primarily
654 attributable to resistance mechanisms, both innate (de novo) and adaptive (acquired), that
655 ultimately compromise treatment effectiveness.

656 In the context of cancer, both cannabinoid receptors and their endogenous ligands are
657 typically overexpressed compared to healthy tissue. However, contradictory data suggest that
658 alterations in this system are context- and tumor type-dependent [21]. Specifically, an association
659 between cannabinoid receptor expression and tumor progression has been established in BC.
660 Thus, decreased CB₁R mRNA levels and increased CB₂R mRNA levels were found in tumor
661 tissue compared to non-tumor mammary epithelial tissue, and the expression of CB₂R was
662 associated with tumor aggressiveness (histological grade) [22]. A subsequent analysis in a larger
663 sample collection revealed that the vast majority of HER2+ breast tumors express CB₂R [20].
664 This pointed to a functional connection between CB₂R and HER2, as it was further demonstrated.
665 Thus, HER2 induces the expression of CB₂R, which then forms heterodimers with HER2,
666 stabilizing it at the plasma membrane by preventing its proteasomal degradation and favoring
667 HER2-driven oncogenic signaling [12]. Directly related to this observation, it has also been
668 reported that the HER2-CB₂R heterodimer has prognostic value in HER2+ BC (its expression in
669 tumor samples obtained before any treatment correlates with poor patient prognosis), and that its
670 disruption triggers antitumor effects [11].

671 Here, we demonstrate that HER2-CB₂R heterodimers are also involved in modulating
672 responsiveness to trastuzumab. Specifically, we show that loss of CB₂R induces a shift in HER2-
673 containing heterodimers, resulting in cancer cells that are less sensitive to the antitumor effects of
674 trastuzumab. Recent studies have established that receptor heterodimerization is a widespread and
675 pivotal mechanism of modulating cell signaling. These dimers have been described not only
676 among RTKs (whose mechanism of activation involves dimerization), but also between GPCRs

677 and even between RTKs and GPCRs [23-25]. The formation of these complexes enhances cellular
678 versatility in response to stimuli, as the signaling properties of receptor heterodimers frequently
679 differ from those of the individual receptors. For CB₂R, heteromers with other GPCRs relevant
680 in cancer, such as CXCR4 [26] or GPR55 [27], have been reported. In these cases, complex
681 formation facilitates cross-antagonism between the protomers.

682 In this study, we observed that trastuzumab resistance is triggered by a shift in the cancer
683 cell receptor heterodimer pattern. Specifically, the loss of CB₂R leads to a decrease in HER2-
684 CB₂R heterodimers that is accompanied by a reduction in HER2-IFNGR1 and an increase in
685 HER2-EGFR expression. This signaling switch makes cancer cells less dependent on HER2 and
686 less responsive to IFN- γ antitumor signaling, while increasing their reliance on EGFR-driven
687 growth and survival pathways. This type of signaling switch is a well-described mechanism by
688 which cancer cells evade the pressure of anticancer drugs and is a common strategy for the
689 acquisition of trastuzumab resistance. Thus, the overexpression of other HER family members
690 (mainly EGFR and HER3), as well as other non-HER RTKs (IGF-1R, c-MET, EphA2, AXL),
691 and non-RTK receptors (EpoR, ER, β 2-AR), has been associated to trastuzumab resistance [9,
692 28]. For example, IGF-1R has been implicated in trastuzumab resistance by forming heterodimers
693 with HER2, which leads to the phosphorylation and activation of HER2 upon IGF-1 binding. Of
694 interest, targeting IGF-1R disrupts the HER2-IGF-1R interaction and restores sensitivity to
695 trastuzumab [29]. Our findings reveal an increase in HER2-EGFR heterodimers with a shift
696 toward EGFR-dependent signaling. The link between trastuzumab resistance and EGFR
697 overexpression is well established in both preclinical models and human BC cases of HER2+ BC.
698 Moreover, this overexpression has been associated with modulation of HER2/EGFR homo- and
699 heterodimerization dynamics, and the dual inhibition of EGFR and HER2 has proved more
700 effective than monospecific agents in overcoming trastuzumab resistance [28]. In fact, several
701 clinical trials have evaluated the antitumor efficacy of dual HER2/EGFR targeting by combining
702 trastuzumab with EGFR inhibitors (such as erlotinib and gefitinib), EGFR-HER2 dual inhibitors
703 (such as lapatinib), pan-HER inhibitors (neratinib, pyrotinib), or anti-EGFR monoclonal

704 antibodies (cetuximab). However, routine clinical practice does not systematically analyze EGFR
705 expression to guide treatment decisions. Our study supports the importance of that systematic
706 analysis as the trastuzumab resistance mechanism described herein may be overcome by
707 simultaneous targeting of HER2 and EGFR.

708 In addition to an increase in HER2-EGFR dimerization, we report that trastuzumab
709 resistance due to CB₂R loss produces a decrease in HER2-IFNGR1 heterodimers. The functional
710 interplay between HER2 and the IFN- γ signaling pathway is well established. For example, IFN-
711 γ reduced plasma membrane HER2 levels (which is associated with diminished growth and
712 induction of tumor senescence) by promoting its proteasomal degradation. Moreover, the
713 combination of anti-HER2 antibodies with IFN- γ synergistically decreased surface HER2
714 expression and impaired tumor growth in an animal model of BC [30]. Furthermore, disruption
715 of IFN- γ signaling by genetic ablation of IFNGR1 conferred resistance to HER2-targeted cell
716 bispecific antibodies and CAR-T cells [31]. Of interest, here we report the existence of HER2-
717 IFNGR1 heterodimers and their involvement in trastuzumab resistance. Specifically, we found
718 that BC cells that become resistant to trastuzumab due to a decrease in CB₂R express less HER2-
719 IFNGR1 dimers and are less responsive to IFN- γ . Although the detailed mechanistic basis for this
720 effect remains to be elucidated, our findings suggest that the physical interaction between HER2
721 and IFNGR1 modulates the signaling properties of both receptors.

722 Our data also suggest that trastuzumab resistance due to CB₂R loss is mediated, at least
723 in part, by blocking the ability of NK cells to induce ADCC, a pivotal mechanism underlying the
724 antitumor activity of trastuzumab. NK cells recognize trastuzumab-opsonized tumor cells via their
725 activating CD16 (Fc γ RIIIa) receptors, triggering their cytotoxic machinery and leading to the
726 release of cytotoxic molecules such as IFN- γ , ultimately resulting in target cell death [4]. A link
727 between trastuzumab resistance and evasion of NK-cell mediated ADCC has been previously
728 described, and several strategies are being explored to boost this immune response and,
729 consequently, overcome trastuzumab resistance [4, 17]. One of these strategies involves
730 optimizing trastuzumab structure by genetically engineering its Fc domain to increase binding to

731 FcγR. However, the monoclonal antibody margetuximab, developed with this approach, did not
732 show therapeutic advantage over trastuzumab in overall survival of patients with previously
733 treated HER2+ advanced BC in the SOPHIA study [32]. Other experimental approaches involve
734 boosting NK cell activity and infiltration, or blocking ADCC inhibitory signals, but none have
735 been routinely implemented in clinical practice yet [4, 17]. In this case, combination therapies are
736 also being considered as a potential means to overcome ADCC evasion and the resulting
737 trastuzumab resistance. Various chemotherapeutic drugs (including anthracyclines,
738 cyclophosphamide, and taxanes) that are used together with or in sequence after HER2-targeting
739 antibody therapies induce immunogenic cell death (ICD), a specific form of apoptosis that directly
740 counteracts ADCC evasion mechanisms. ICD is characterized by the release of damage-
741 associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) such as HMGB1, which has been shown to enhance NK
742 cell activation and recruitment to tumors. In addition, *in vitro* treatment with anthracyclines and
743 taxanes enhanced anti-HER2 monoclonal antibody-induced ADCC by promoting endoplasmic
744 reticulum stress and upregulating NKG2D-ligands in BC cells [4, 17].

745 Our findings also highlight combination approaches as a promising strategy to overcome
746 trastuzumab resistance due to CB₂R loss. On the one hand, we have demonstrated that
747 simultaneous (or sequential) targeting of EGFR and HER2 resensitizes resistant cells to the
748 antitumor effect of trastuzumab. In addition, previous studies have shown that cannabinoids elicit
749 antitumor responses in preclinical models of cancer, including HER2+ BC, suggesting the
750 potential benefit of combining them with trastuzumab. The antitumor effects of cannabinoids rely
751 on their ability to inhibit cancer cell proliferation, induce their apoptotic death, suppress
752 angiogenesis, and reduce the invasive and migratory capacities of tumor cells, thereby lowering
753 their metastatic potential [18, 19]. The vast preclinical research consistently demonstrating these
754 effects has set the bases for the clinical study of these compounds as antitumor agents in
755 glioblastoma.

756 In summary, this study identifies a novel mechanism underlying trastuzumab resistance,
757 in which the ECS —specifically through CB₂R— plays a pivotal role. In addition, our findings

758 highlight the functional significance of heteromeric receptor patterns in cancer cells, suggesting
759 that, analogous to molecular signatures associated with BC subtypes, heterodimer signatures may
760 possess predictive value. Finally, elucidation of this mechanism supports the potential
761 development of new therapeutic strategies to overcome resistance based on the simultaneous or
762 sequential targeting of EGFR and HER2, reinforcing the potential clinical utility of routine EGFR
763 expression analysis to optimize treatment selection for individual patients.

764

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781

782 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

783 EP-G and CS conceptualized the project, coordinated and supervised the research. MS-V, SAB,
784 SB-B, IT, MRH, NGM-I, FP-D and MT-D performed most of the experiments and analyzed the

785 corresponding results. AM-C and RB performed the proteomic studies; SJH, LEK, SP and NK
786 designed the trastuzumab NanoBiT competition binding experiments. LEK and IP performed the
787 competition-binding assays; SP designed and generated the HiBiT and LrgBiT HER2 and CB₂R
788 constructs.; OMA the experiments related with co-cultures. DG-D and IPC assisted in the
789 generation of the CB₂R KO cell line. CG-L, DG-F, GS-E, AJS-L, ER-M, MCRP, BAP-C and LM
790 provided the patient samples included in the TMAs. SZ performed some of the EGFR
791 immunostainings. NL-E assisted with the statistical analyses. SJH, SC-L, MS and MG provided
792 study materials and resources. CS wrote the manuscript, that was revised by MS-V, MS, SC-L,
793 EJH, MG and EP-G. All authors reviewed the final manuscript.

794

795 **COMPETING INTEREST**

796 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

797

798 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

799 The data generated in this study are available within the article and its additional data files. The
800 proteomic datasets generated in HEK293T cells are available in PRoteomics IDentifications
801 Database (PRIDE, accession number PXD065700), and the RNAseq datasets generated BT474-
802 derived cell lines in Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO, accession number GSE300749).

803

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922

923

924

925 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

926 **Figure 1. A reduction in HER2-CB₂R and CB₂R expression after NAT is linked to treatment**
927 **resistance.** (A) Representative Proximity Ligation Assay (PLA) images of human samples
928 exhibiting high and low HER2-CB₂R heteromer expression. Red: PLA signal; blue: nuclear
929 staining (DAPI). Scale bar, 25 μ m. (B) Kaplan-Meier plots of disease-free survival for samples
930 obtained after NAT and included in the tissue microarrays from Hospitals 12 de Octubre (TMA
931 H12O) and Puerta de Hierro (TMA HPH). (C) Relative HER2-CB₂R expression, as determined
932 by PLA, in matched TMA samples. The left data columns in each panel represent samples from
933 patients with no long-term disease progression, while the right columns represent the non-
934 responders. Lines connect paired samples from the same patient before (PRE) and after (POST)
935 NAT. (D) Kaplan-Meier plots of disease-free survival, stratified by type of change in HER2-
936 CB₂R dimer expression after NAT, in samples from the indicated TMAs. HER2 (E) and CB₂R
937 (G) expression, as determined by IHC, in samples from TMA H12O and TMA HPH, represented
938 as indicated in panel (C). Kaplan-Meier plots of disease-free survival, stratified by changes in
939 HER2 (F) or CB₂R expression (G) after NAT, in samples from the indicated TMAs.

940

941 **Figure 2. Loss of CB₂R leads to trastuzumab resistance.** (A) Viability of BT474-derived cell
942 lines in response to trastuzumab. TS: trastuzumab-sensitive; TR: trastuzumab-resistant; TR-
943 CB₂R: TR with overexpression of CB₂R. (B) Representative PLA images of HER2-CB₂R (left)
944 and quantification of PLA signal (right, n = 3). Red: PLA signal; blue: nuclear staining (DAPI).
945 Scale bar, 50 μ m. (C and E) mRNA expression of HER2 (*ERBB2*) and CB₂R (*CNR2*) in the
946 indicated cell lines, as determined by qPCR. SCR: Scramble (TS cells); CB₂R KO: TS cells with
947 genetic deletion of CB₂R; RESC: CB₂R KO cells reinfected with CB₂R. (D) CB₂R expression, as
948 determined by Western blot. The densitometric analysis is shown next to representative
949 luminograms. (F) Representative HER2-CB₂R PLA images (left) and quantification (right). Scale
950 bar, 50 μ m. (G) Cell viability in response to trastuzumab treatment for 5 days. All data, except
951 for those in panels (C) and (E) (*CNR2*), were normally distributed and analyzed using two-tailed
952 ANOVAs [two-way in panels (A) and (G); one-way in panels (B), (D), (E) (*ERBB2*), and (F)].

953 Non-normally distributed data were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis test. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p <$
954 0.01 , *** $p < 0.01$ vs. TS (A) or SCR (G); # $p < 0.05$, ### $p < 0.001$ vs. TR (A) or CB₂R KO (G).
955 **Figure 3. Trastuzumab resistance does not depend on differential affinity for HER2-HER2**
956 **versus HER2-CB₂R dimers.** (A) Binding of trastuzumab conjugated to fluorescein
957 isothiocyanate (trastuzumab-FITC) to HER2, as determined by flow cytometry, in the indicated
958 cell lines. (B-C) Representative luminograms of protein expression analysis of total HER2 by
959 Western blot (B) and of membrane-bound HER2 by biotinylating (C). Densitometry values were
960 normalized to β -Actin (B), or to both Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase and β -Actin (C) and are presented in the
961 graphs on the right (B) or below (C). (D) Competition NanoBiT ligand-binding studies between
962 trastuzumab-FITC (10 nM) and unlabelled trastuzumab to HiBiT-HER2 – LrgBiT-HER2 (grey
963 circles) or HiBiT-HER2 – LrgBiT-CB₂R (orange circles) expressed in HEK293T (left panel; n=5)
964 or CHO-K1 (right panel; n=3) cells. Data are expressed as % of total trastuzumab-FITC binding
965 in the absence of competitor (100%) and vehicle alone (0%). pKi values are shown in the table
966 below the graphs. All data were normally distributed and were analyzed by Student's *t*-test or
967 one-way ANOVA (D).

968

969 **Figure 4: Identification of signaling routes involved in trastuzumab resistance due to**
970 **reduced HER2-CB₂R.** (A) Representative co-immunoprecipitation (co-IP) blot of proteins from
971 HEK293T wild-type (WT) cells and WT-derived lines stably expressing HER2, HA-tagged CB₂R
972 or both. (B) Venn diagram illustrating proteins identified as potential interactors of CB₂R, HER2,
973 or the HER2-CB₂R complex using PD software. (C) Key signaling pathways modulated by the
974 123 proteins selectively interacting with the HER2-CB₂R dimer, as identified by Reactome
975 software. (D) Relative expression of differentially expressed genes in trastuzumab-sensitive (TS
976 and SCR) and resistant (TR and CB₂R KO) cell lines, determined by RNA sequencing (RNAseq).
977 (E) Oncogenesis-related gene signatures differentially expressed between sensitive and resistant
978 cell lines. Results are shown as variation against the resistant lines and therefore positive values
979 indicate pathways overrepresented in sensitive lines, while negative values indicate pathways
980 underrepresented in sensitive lines (and thus overrepresented in resistant cells). (F) Gene Set

981 Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) of the RNAseq samples. The green line represents the enrichment
982 ratio. NES = normalized enrichment score.

983

984 **Figure 5. CB₂R loss-driven trastuzumab resistance is associated with impaired antitumor**
985 **IFN- γ signaling.** (A-D) mRNA (A-B) and protein (C-D) expression, as determined by qPCR and
986 Western blot, respectively, of different components of the IFN- γ /JAK/STAT pathway in the
987 indicated cell lines. The densitometric analysis of the WB experiments in (C-D) is shown next to
988 representative luminograms. In (D), cells were exposed to IFN- γ for 6 h. (E) Cancer cell viability
989 following 24 h co-culture with the NK cell line NK92-CD16-GFP and 1 h trastuzumab exposure.
990 Control groups (-NK cells; first three bars in each panel) represent cancer cells cultured in the
991 absence of NK cells. The viability of the corresponding vehicle-treated cells was set at 100% and
992 is represented as a horizontal dotted line. (F) IFN- γ levels in the extracellular medium of the co-
993 cultures described in (E), as determined by ELISA. All data, except for those in panels (A)
994 (*IFNGR1* TS group), (C) (STAT1) and (D) (pSTAT1 and IRF1) were normally distributed and
995 analyzed using two-tailed one-way ANOVA and a Student's *t*-test [in (F)]. Non-normally
996 distributed data were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis test.

997

998 **Figure 6. Trastuzumab resistance driven by CB₂R downregulation relies on HER2**
999 **heterodimer reorganization.** (A) Representative HER2-IFNGR1 PLA images (left) and
1000 quantification (right) in the BT474-derived cells before and after IFN- γ treatment. Red: PLA
1001 signal; blue: nuclear staining (DAPI). Scale bar, 50 μ m. (B) mRNA expression levels, determined
1002 by qPCR, of HER receptor family members. (C) Representative Western blot analysis (left) and
1003 densitometry quantification (right) of EGFR expression. (D) Representative HER2-EGFR PLA
1004 images (left) and quantification (right) in the BT474-derived cell lines. (E) Viability of the
1005 indicated cell lines in response to the selective EGFR inhibitor erlotinib. (F) Competition
1006 NanoBiT ligand-binding studies between trastuzumab-FITC (10 nM) and unlabelled trastuzumab
1007 to HiBiT-HER2 – LrgBiT-HER2 (grey circles) or HiBiT-EGFR – LrgBiT-HER2 (orange circles)
1008 expressed in HEK293T (left panel; n=5) or CHO-K1 (right panel; n=3) cells. Data are expressed

1009 as % of total trastuzumab-FITC binding in the absence of competitor (100%) and vehicle alone
1010 (0%). All data were normally distributed and analyzed using two-tailed ANOVAs [two-way in
1011 panel (E); one-way in the rest of panels]. *** $p < 0.01$ vs. TS (left) or SCR (right); # $p < 0.05$,
1012 ### $p < 0.001$ vs. TR (left) or CB₂R KO (right).

1013

1014 **Figure 7. High post-NAT HER2-EGFR heterodimer burden predicts poor treatment**

1015 **outcomes.** (A) Representative Proximity Ligation Assay (PLA) images of human samples
1016 exhibiting high and low HER2-EGFR heteromer expression. Red: PLA signal; blue: nuclear
1017 staining (DAPI). Scale bar, 50 μ m. (B) Kaplan-Meier plots of disease-free survival for samples
1018 obtained after NAT and included in the tissue microarrays from Hospitals 12 de Octubre (TMA
1019 H12O) and Puerta de Hierro (TMA HPH). (C) Relative HER2-EGFR expression, as determined
1020 by PLA, in matched TMA samples. The left data columns in each panel represent samples from
1021 patients with no long-term disease progression, while the right columns represent the non-
1022 responders. Lines connect paired samples from the same patient before (PRE) and after (POST)
1023 NAT. (D) Kaplan-Meier plots of disease-free survival, stratified by type of change in HER2-
1024 EGFR dimer expression after NAT, in samples from the indicated TMAs. (E) Relative EGFR
1025 expression, as determined by PLA, in matched TMA samples before (PRE) and after NAT
1026 (POST). Data are represented as in C. (F) Kaplan-Meier plots of disease-free survival, stratified
1027 by type of change in EGFR expression after NAT.

1028

1029 **Figure 8. Trastuzumab resistance linked to reduced CB₂R is overcome by targeting EGFR**
1030 **and HER2 signaling, and by non-CB₂R-selective cannabinoid treatments.** (A) Viability of

1031 the indicated cell lines in response to trastuzumab and erlotinib treatment (alone or in
1032 combination) for 4 days. The viability of the corresponding vehicle-treated cells was set at 100%
1033 and is represented as a dotted horizontal line. (B) Representative Western blot (top) and
1034 densitometric quantification (bottom) of protein expression profiles following a 3-day treatment
1035 with erlotinib (5 μ M), IFN- γ (20 ng/mL, 6h) or the combination. (C) CB₂R mRNA expression, as
1036 determined by qPCR in response to erlotinib treatment. (D) Representative HER2-CB₂R PLA

1037 images (left) and quantification (right). Red: PLA signal; blue: nuclear staining (DAPI). Scale
1038 bar, 50 μm . (E-F) Tumor growth in nude female mice bearing subcutaneous xenografts generated
1039 by injection of the indicated cell lines. (G) Viability of the indicated cell lines in response to the
1040 CB₂R-selective agonist HU308, THC (a CB₁R/CB₂R-mixed agonist) and three different cannabis
1041 preparations (CE1, CE2 and CE3) for 1 day. The viability of the corresponding vehicle-treated
1042 cells was set at 100%. CE1 and CE2 were THC rich extracts, while CE3 contained a 1:1
1043 THC:CBD ratio. The precise composition of the three CEs is shown in Supp. Table S2. All data
1044 were normally distributed and analyzed using two-tailed one-way ANOVAs (A, B, and G) or
1045 Student's *t*-test (C-G). In (A) and (B), the p values right above the bars correspond to comparisons
1046 with vehicle-treated cells.

Fig. 1

A

B

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Fig. 2

Fig. 3

A

B

C

D

	HiBiT HER2 - LrgBiT HER2	HiBiT HER2 - LrgBiT CB_2R	p value
HEK293T	9.51 ± 0.10	9.29 ± 0.10	0.256
CHO-K1	9.65 ± 0.03	9.46 ± 0.18	0.531

Fig. 4

A

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E

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Fig. 5

A

B

C

D

E

F

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

A

B

C

D

E

F

Fig. 8

